

and more insect and disease resistances than local check NN7A.

OM91, from the cross 900/IR747, has a 90-95 d growth duration, compact tillering, and slender white grain. Yields averaged 5.8 t/ha in the 1984-86 CLRRRI and multilocation yield trials (Table 1).

OM91 is highly resistant to brown planthopper biotype 2 and to blast (BI). It withstood high BI pressure in Binh Minh district, Cuu Long Province, seed station trials (Table 2).

OM91 was released for large-scale cultivation in the Cuu Long Delta in 1987. □

Table 2. Reaction of OM91 to insect pest and disease^a in Cuu Long Delta in 1984-85.

Variety	Brown planthopper		Blast					
			Hau Giang		An Giang		Cuu Long	
			Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction
OM91	3	R	2	R	2-3	R-MR	2-3	R-MR
NN7A	3	R	8	HS	8	HS	9	HS
NN6A	3	R	9	HS	9	HS	9	HS

^aArtificial infestation, using IRRI test and scoring procedures. R = resistant, HS = highly susceptible. Resistant check for BPH = IR36, BI = IR. Susceptible check for BPH = TN1, BI = NN7A.

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Performance of IR42 in deepwater rice areas on the Red River delta in northern Vietnam

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Rice variety IR42 was introduced in Vietnam in 1977. We compared it with some other varieties in the wet season (Jun-Oct) field trials (Table 1).

In 1987 wet season in Ha Nam Ninh, Ha Bac, and some other deepwater rice areas of the Red River delta, about 3,400 ha of IR42 was grown in medium water depth (30-40 cm), next to some widely grown local varieties (Moc Tuyen, Bao Thai, and others). We studied its performance in three districts.

IR42 (30 d old) was transplanted with about 10 t farmyard manure (60 kg N)/ha and 17.6 kg P/ha (no K).

Damage by pests and diseases was not significant.

In 46 samples of IR42 and 21 samples of Moc Tuyen from farmers' fields, we found the following:

IR42 yields averaged more than 5 t/ha in 22% of the samples, 4-5 t/ha in 61%, and 3-4 t/ha in 17%.

Moc Tuyen yields were higher than 5 t/ha in 19% of the samples, 4-5 t/ha in 29%, and 3-4 t/ha in 52%.

Table 1. Yield trials in 1977-83 wet season.^a

Year	Av grain yield (t/ha)			
	IR42	IR22	BR52-87-1	Moc Tuyen ^b
1977	4.6	4.0	—	—
1978	4.9	3.8	—	—
1979	5.1	5.3	—	—
1980	4.7	3.8	—	—
1982	5.9	—	5.5	—
1983	2.7	—	—	2.3

^aSource: National Institute of Agricultural Sciences. ^bPhotoperiod-sensitive, China variety.

Table 2. Av grain yield by sowing dates of IR42 in 1987 wet season.

Sowing date	Samples (no.) by average yield			
	Over 5.0 t/ha	4.5-5.0 t/ha	4.0-4.5 t/ha	Less than 4.0 t/ha
25-30 May	6	3	4	—
1-5 Jun	2	2	3	—
6-10 Jun	2	6	6	6
11-15 Jun	—	3	1	2

IR42 responded to time of seeding (Table 2). Most crops that yielded more than 5 t/ha were sown 25-30 May; crops

with less than 4 t/ha were sown 6-15 Jun. Best seeding time was late May to early Jun. □

Seed technology

Standardizing hybrid rice A line seed production

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A trial to standardize A line seed production techniques was conducted in summer 1986. Zhen Shan 97 A was used as the B line in the ratios 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 4:1, 5:1, and 6:1. To synchronize flowering and prolong pollen supply, alternate hills of B line were pruned